

EFFECTS OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON ELECTRO-FUSION JOINING BEHAVIOR OF CF/PPS COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Thermoplastic composite, Electro-fusion welding, Joining behavior, Polyphenylene sulfide, Welding area*

1 Introduction

Continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic (cFRTP) composites which can be manufactured with press-forming are attracting attention recently in aircraft and automobile applications. However, cFRTP components have rather simple geometry due to the limited deformation allowed for the reinforcing fibers and high viscosity of the resin, and thus require joining as an indispensable step in the manufacturing process of cFRTP. Moreover the demand of on-site joining without facilities is also expected for a large-scale cFRTP structures. Conventional joining methods used for thermosetting composites such as mechanically fastening and adhesive bonding are not capable of applying for cFRTP components, because those methods have some drawbacks in strength and reliability, such as stress concentration and interlayer delamination. To solve the above-mentioned problems, the joining technologies such as ultrasonic welding, resistance welding and induction welding have been proposed for high performance cFRTP [1-3]. However, these methods require the fixed equipment for electric power and pressing, and then it is associated with difficulty in utilizing for a large structures and complex shaped components. In this study, the electro-fusion welding behavior of UD-CF/PPS and woven-CF/PPS laminates jointed using the Ni-Cr wire as a resistance heating element was investigated.

2 Material and experimental procedure

2.1 Materials

The materials used for the experiment are two kinds of CF/PPS laminates (TenCate, CETEX[®]) as shown in Table 1. One has a unidirectional construction with a fiber content of $V_f=60\text{vol}\%$ (UD-CF/PPS),

and the other has 5H sateen weave construction with a fiber content of $V_f=45\text{vol}\%$ (Woven-CF/PPS).

Table1 Materials used for test specimen

ID	UD-CF/PPS	Woven-CF/PPS
Fiber content, V_f [vol%]	60	45
Reinforcing configuration	Unidirectional	5H-sateen weave
Stacking sequence	$[0]_8$	$[0/90]_4$
Surface image		

2.2 Specimen and welding method

Figure 1 shows the appearance of electro-fusion welding. The test specimens with $W=20\text{mm}$ in width and $L=70\text{mm}$ in length were prepared. The welding area is insofar as $L_f=20\text{mm}$ from the end of laminates. A straight Ni-Cr wire with $\phi=0.2\text{mm}$ in diameter and $L_w=30\text{mm}$ in length was mounted between laminates to work as the heating element. To investigate the effects of thickness of PPS films on electro-fusion behavior, the PPS films (Toray Co., Ltd., TORELINA[®], $t_{PPS}=0.1\text{mm}$) were inserted welding interface as shown in Figure 2.

The test specimen was clipped by insulating plates made of ceramics and the superimposed voltage controlled by a AC converter (Yamabishi denki Co., Ltd., S-130-20) was applied to Ni-Cr wire. This made generate a joule heat in the joint interface between laminates, thus made melt the PPS resin around the Ni-Cr wire. To prevent an electric

leakage between the test specimen and electrode, polyimide film (Du Pont-Toray Co., Ltd., Kapton® Type H, 0.05mm in thickness) which possesses high heat resistance and electrical resistance was inserted as shown in Figure 1.

In this study, three Ni-Cr wires were also used as heating element to expand the welding area. In such case, the distance of Ni-Cr wires (L_{Ni-Cr}) was changed from 1.0 to 6.0mm.

Fig.1 Appearance of electro-fusion welding device.

Fig.2 Insert method of PPS film and Ni-Cr wire.

2.3 Evaluation method

The images of joint surfaces peeled off after joining were imported with a scanner device (Epson Co., Ltd., ES-7000H), and the welding area (A_w) and the profile shapes of welding area were measured by image analysis as shown in Figure 3. The joint surfaces and cross-sectional surfaces were also observed with a scanning electron microscope (Keyence Co., Ltd., VE-7800). Test specimens were monitored on the top and side surfaces with an infrared thermography (Apiste Co., Ltd., FSV-1200) to predict a distribution of temperature rise of the joint part when it turned on electricity without loading pressure.

Fig.3 Measuring area for evaluation of welding area.

The single lap shear strength (LSS) test was carried out to evaluate a joint strength of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ and woven-CF/PPS laminates by using universal testing machine (SHIMAZU CO., Ltd., AGS-X). Figure 4 shows appearance of lap shear strength test specimen. Before LSS testing, aluminum tabs were bonded to end of specimens with epoxy adhesive.

Fig.4 Geometry of single lap joining test specimen.

The cross-head speed was $v=1\text{mm/min}$. The LSS was calculated by using two equations:

$$\text{Active } \tau = \frac{P}{A_w} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Apparent } \tau = \frac{P}{A_L} \quad (2)$$

where τ , lap shear strength [MPa]; A_w , welding area [mm^2]; A_L , overlap area [mm] and P , maximum tensile force [N]. The influence of inserted PPS films to welding interface was investigated using three Ni-Cr wires.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 In case of single Ni-Cr wire

3.1.1 Effect of applied voltage

Figure 5 shows the effects of applied voltage on the welding area at $t=60\text{s}$ and $t_{PPS}=0\text{mm}$. In both UD-

CF/PPS and woven-CF/PPS laminates, the welding area tends to increase exponentially with increasing the applied voltage. This seems to be valid from Joule's law which the heat is generated by the square of voltage applying through a conductor of electrical resistance for a time. However the electrical resistance is dependent on fiber reinforcing configuration, then the fusion area is affected by a varied heat quantity. In case of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$, the welding developed preferentially along the width direction of test specimen as shown in Figure 6 (a), because the Ni-Cr wire is mounted along the longitudinal direction of carbon fiber, and a current leakage is likely to occur from Ni-Cr wire to carbon fiber. When the voltage was applied over $E=4.0V$, PPS matrix vaporized along the fiber and the exposure of fiber are visible on the joint surface. It was impossible for over-current protection to test at the voltage applied over $E=5.0V$. UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ exhibits smaller welding area than UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$ at any applied voltages. The welding area of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ laminates was extended to $A_w=280mm^2$ at $E=8.0V$, which Ni-Cr wire was heated to red heat in the joint interface. The area heated by Ni-Cr wire and area whitened by thermal deformation are visible in Fig.6 (b). It is considered that the joule heat arose in fiber bundles by leaking a current from Ni-Cr wire to the carbon fiber, and then melted area of PPS matrix was extended along the fiber direction and the fiber bundles spread laterally by pressing. In case of the woven-CF/PPS, on the

other hand, the welding area was increased rapidly at the lower applied voltages compared to the UD-CF/PPS ones. The corners of a triangle marked at both sides and the resultant joint surface blacked as shown in Fig.6 (c). Therefore it is obvious that the welding area is affected remarkably by fiber configuration on the joint surface in addition to the applied voltage.

Fig.5 Effects of applied voltage on welding area.

Fig.6 Images of joint surface peeled off after joining.

3.1.2 Infrared thermography observation

Figure 7 shows temperature distribution of CF/PPS laminate surfaces which were measured by infrared thermography. In case of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$, the temperature on laminate surface was higher ($T>300^\circ C$) along the Ni-Cr wires as shown in Fig.7 (a). This is because it was heated by the joule heat in the carbon fiber. The heat transfer of UD-CF/PPS ($\theta=90^\circ$) to the fiber direction exhibits higher than UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$ one as shown in Fig.7 (b). The temperature on the laminate surface was about $T=230^\circ C$. In case of woven-CF/PPS laminates, the high temperature distribution of about $T=230^\circ C$ is visible at at the edge of Ni-Cr wire. Also, the edge of Ni-Cr wire reached higher temperature than the center of laminate surface.

Fig.7 Temperature distribution of laminate surfaces ($E=4.5V$, $t=60s$).

3.1.3 Profile shapes of fusion area and cross-sectional observation

Figure 8 shows the profile shapes of a fusion area at various applied voltage $t=60s$. In case of UD-CF/PPS laminates, the fusion area tends to increase uniformly along the fiber direction with increasing the applied voltage as shown in Fig.8 (a) and (b). When the fiber orientation angle was $\theta=90^\circ$, a width of melting line decreased near the edge of Ni-Cr wire because heat loss from the electrode ($x=-10, 10$) occurred. Also, in Woven-CF/PPS laminates under $E=4.0V$, it is observed significantly that the PPS resin was melted only near the edge of Ni-Cr wire as shown in Fig.8 (c). This is due to flow a current locally the electrode ($x=-10, 10$), and the leak current from the Ni-Cr wire occurred in an exposed area of carbon fiber. However, the welding area increased in the central part of welding surfaces ($x=-2.5\sim 2.5$) at $E=5.0V$ where it was heated by the joule heat in the carbon fiber. Figure 9 shows the cross-sectional SEM images of UD and woven-CF/PPS laminates applied at $E=4.0V$ and $t=60s$. The UD-CF/PPS laminates has many pores and the disarray of carbon fibers at the interface between Ni-Cr wire and laminates as shown in Fig.9 (a). To further improve the quality of welding interface, it is necessary to increase the resin content by adding a

Fig.8 Profile shapes of a fusion area at various applied voltage ($t=60s$).

Fig.9 Cross-sectional SEM images ($E=4.0V$, $t=60s$).

resin film in the welding interface. In woven-CF/PPS ones, on the other hand, any pores and defects are not visible as shown in Fig.9 (b).

3.1.4 Electro-fusion mechanism

Figure 10 shows the mechanism diagram of electro-fusion process of UD and woven laminates using single Ni-Cr wire. In the case of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$, (i) the current leakage is likely to occur from Ni-Cr wire to carbon fiber; (ii) the carbon fiber generated high joule heat around the Ni-Cr wire; (iii) a gasification and thermal degradation of PPS resin arose around the Ni-Cr wire. In case of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$, (i) immediately after conducting to Ni-Cr wire, the PPS polymer melted around the Ni-Cr wire; (ii) the heat transfer occurs in the carbon fiber direction after conducting. UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$

		(i) Preparation	(ii) Conducting	(iii) Transferring	(iv) Complete
(a) UD CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$	Model	Ni-Cr wire Laminate Fiber direction →	Welding area I →	Joule heat of CF I →	Gasification of resin
	Scan image				
(b) UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$	Model	Ni-Cr wire Laminate Fiber direction ↑	Welding area I →	Heat transfer I →	Expanding of welding area
	Scan image				
(c) Woven-CF/PPS	Model	Ni-Cr wire Laminate	Welding area I → Current leakage	Edge effect I → Heat transfer	
	Scan image				

Fig.10 Mechanism diagram of electro-fusion process.

occurred lower current leakage than UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$; (iii) the welding area is expanded to fiber direction. In case of woven-CF/PPS, (i) when the voltage is applied to Ni-Cr wires, the current leakage occurs between Ni-Cr wire and carbon fiber bundles; (ii) an edge effect occurs around the end of Ni-Cr wire. In case of woven laminates, the edge effect occur significantly compared to UD laminate's one.; (iii) the welding area is increased by heat transfer and joule heating of carbon fiber. It is considered that the reason why the edge effect occurs at the end of Ni-Cr wire is because it is easy to flow through current.

3.1.5 Prevention of current leakage

Figure 11 shows the effects of thickness of PPS films on welding area at $E=4.5V$ and $t=60s$. In case of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$, the welding area tends to decrease slightly with increasing the thickness of PPS film from $A_w=65\text{mm}^2$ to 60mm^2 . UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ shows different trends compared with UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$. When the thickness of PPS film was not inserted, the welding area became the largest ($A_w=68\text{mm}^2$), because the heat transfer was carried out directly to fiber direction. When the thickness of PPS resin was over $t_{PPS}=0.2\text{mm}$, the welding area was decreased up to $A_w=25\text{mm}^2$.

(a) UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$ and 90°

(b) Woven-CF/PPS

Fig. 11 Effects of thickness of PPS films on welding area ($E=4.5V$, $t=60s$).

	Thickness of PPS film, t_{PPS} [mm]			
	0	0.2	0.4	0.6
UD $\theta=0^\circ$				
UD $\theta=90^\circ$				
Woven				

Fig. 12 Scan images of CF/PPS laminates using PPS films ($E=4.5V$, $t=60s$).

In case of woven-CF/PPS, the edge effect occurs around of end of Ni-Cr wire when the thickness of PPS film was under $t_{PPS}=0.2\text{mm}$ as shown in Figure 12. It is obvious that the current leakage can be prevented at over $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$. When the thickness of PPS film was $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$, the welding area was achieved $A_w=70\text{mm}^2$. However, in case of not less than $t_{PPS}=0.6\text{mm}$, the welding area was decreased for the reason the thickness of PPS films is thick. It is considered that the current leakage from Ni-Cr wires to carbon fiber bundles is prevented excessively.

3.2 In case of multiple Ni-Cr wires

3.2.1 Effect of distance of Ni-Cr wires

Figure 13 shows the effects of distance of Ni-Cr wires on welding area at $E=4.5\text{V}$, $t=60\text{s}$ and $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$. Three Ni-Cr wires were used to be

increased the welding area. Only UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ and woven-CF/PPS were investigated because UD-CF/PPS $\theta=0^\circ$ laminates were difficult to remove welding surfaces. UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ arose overheating at under $L_{Ni-Cr}=2\text{mm}$ as shown in Fig.13 (a) and Figure 14. The best welding condition was obtained at $L_{Ni-Cr}=4\text{mm}$. Then the welding area was $A_w=250\text{mm}^2$. When the distance of Ni-Cr wires was over $L_{Ni-Cr}=6\text{mm}$, the imperfect welding area arose between Ni-Cr wires. Therefore the welding area was decreased linearly as shown in Fig.13 (a). In case of woven-CF/PPS, when the distance of Ni-Cr wires is under $L_{Ni-Cr}=3\text{mm}$, the welding area is constant as shown in Fig.13 (b). Also, the edge effect occurs at $L_{Ni-Cr}=1\text{mm}$. At $L_{Ni-Cr}=4\text{mm}$, on the other hand, the welding area is achieved $A_w=250\text{mm}^2$. In addition, the edge effects and imperfect welding

(a) UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$

(b) Woven-CF/PPS

Fig.13 Effects of distance of Ni-Cr wires on welding area ($E=4.5\text{V}$, $t=60\text{s}$, $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$).

Fig.14 Scan images of welding surface ($E=4.5\text{V}$, $t=60\text{s}$, $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$).

zone were not seen in joining interface. However, the imperfect welding area arose at over $L_{Ni-Cr}=5\text{mm}$.

3.2.2 Effect of applied voltage

Figure 15 shows the effects of distance of Ni-Cr wires on welding area at $L_{Ni-Cr}=4\text{mm}$ and $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$. In both test specimens, the welding area was increased with increasing the applied voltage as shown in Fig.15. Also, the imperfect welding area occurred between the Ni-Cr wires when the applied voltage was under $E=4.0\text{V}$. It is considered that the best applied voltage was $E=4.5\text{V}$ in both test specimens from scan images of welding surface. When the applied voltage was over $E=5.0\text{V}$, the welding area was increased. However it was observed that a thermal degradation of PPS polymer and thermal deformation of the laminates arose around the heating elements.

(a) UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$

(b) Woven-CF/PPS

Fig.15 Effects of applied voltage on welding area ($t=60\text{s}$, $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$, $L_{Ni-Cr}=4\text{mm}$).

3.2.3 Electro-fusion mechanism

Figure 17 shows mechanism diagram of electro-fusion process using multiple Ni-Cr wires and inserted PPS films. In UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ and woven-CF/PPS laminates, it was considered that the electro-fusion mechanism is the same principle. The electro-fusion mechanism was divided into the three steps. (i) Soon after starting the conducting to Ni-Cr wires, the melting of PPS polymer arises around the Ni-Cr wires. (ii) Subsequently, when the carbon fiber of CF RTP laminates is exposed to welding interface, the current leakage occurs from Ni-Cr wires to carbon fibers. Then, the welding area is increased by a heat transfer and a joule heat of carbon fiber and Ni-Cr wires. (iii) The melting of PPS polymer between each Ni-Cr wire is carried out completely by lengthening the welding time. At that time, the electro-fusion joining is completed.

Fig.16 Scan images of welding surface ($t=60\text{s}$, $t_{PPS}=0.4\text{mm}$, $L_{Ni-Cr}=4\text{mm}$).

Fig.17 Mechanism diagram of electro-fusion process using multiple Ni-Cr wires and inserted PPS films.

3.2.4 Single lap shear strength (LSS)

Table 2 shows welding conditions of *LSS* test specimens. The single lap shear strength (*LSS*) of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ and woven-CF/PPS laminates is plotted in Figure 18. The fracture surfaces of UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ and woven-CF/PPS laminates are also presented in Figure 19. The maximum load of the test specimens which inserted the PPS films in the welding interface was smaller than the test specimen which is not inserted the films as shown in Fig.18 (a). Also, the lap shear strength shows the same tendency compared to the maximum load as shown in Fig.18 (b). It was observed that the existence of the PPS films in the welding interface weakened the lap shear strength. In case of Non-film laminates, it is considered that the matrix polymer of welding surface enough melted around the Ni-Cr wires as shown in Fig.19. As a general tendency, *Active* τ is also larger than *Apparent* τ . As for UD-NonFilm, *LSS* achieved *Active* $\tau=23.5\text{MPa}$ and *Apparent* $\tau=17.9\text{MPa}$. The profile shape of welding area was good quality as shown in Fig.19. On the

other hand, in case of woven-CF/PPS Non-film, *LSS* achieved *Active* $\tau=18.5\text{MPa}$ and *Apparent* $\tau=16.3\text{MPa}$, but the welding surface arose edge effect.

Table 2 Welding condition of *LSS* test specimens

Test specimens	UD-CF/PPS $\theta=90^\circ$ Woven-CF/PPS
Applied voltage, E [V]	4.5
Holding time, t [s]	60
Number of Ni-Cr wires, n_{Ni-Cr}	3
Distance of Ni-Cr wires, L_{Ni-Cr} [mm]	4
Thickness of PPS resin, t_{PPS} [mm]	Non or 0.4

(a) P - δ curve

(b) Lap shear strength (*LSS*)

Fig.18 Result of single lap shear strength (*LSS*) test.

Fig.19 Fracture surfaces of CF/PPS laminates.

4 Conclusions

In this study, the electric-fusion behavior of cFRTP composites when Ni-Cr wire was used as a resistance heating element was investigated for UD and woven CF/PPS laminates. It was concluded that the fiber reinforcing configurations had a considerable influence on the fusion behavior. It was found that the insertion of PPS films in welding interface was required in order to prevent the edge effect and non-uniform profile shapes of the welding area. On the other hand, the result of a single lap shear strength (LSS), the maximum load and LSS of the test specimens which inserted the PPS films in the welding interface was smaller than the test specimen which is not inserted the films.

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